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Determinants of Social Entrepreneurship in Rural West Java: The Role of Agent of Change, Technology and Innovations, and Communication Chanel

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Abstract

The aim of the research is study examines the determinants of social entrepreneurship. These variables are characteristics of reform agents, characteristics of technology and innovation, communication channels, community dialogue, and collective action so that they can shape changes in behavior related to the creation of social entrepreneurship in the MHP program. This study used a mixed methods approach. Samples were taken of 200 people, processing and analysis data using SEM-PLS. The results of the SEM analysis show three structural equations, (1) depicting that X1 has a significant direct effect on Y1 (0.248) and X2 (0.518). This factor is dominant in the field because the characteristics of technology and innovation provide opportunities for social innovation. Equation (2) shows that Y1 influences Y2 (0.292), this shows that in community dialogue, the community invited to choose who will manage and maintain the turbine. Equation (3) Y1 has a direct effect on the level of social entrepreneurship (0.671), while Y2 has a negative effect (-0.199). The reason is almost 90 percent of the public when there is a communication dialogue in a large meeting, accepts a decision if there is already someone who is considered far more understanding. Community dialogue influenced by the characteristics of change agents as well as the characteristics of technology and innovation. Collective action are influenced by the support of community dialogue, while social entrepreneurship is influenced by communication dialogue and collective action. Community dialogue and collective action are driving forces for citizens to make changes in social entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Collective Action, Community Dialogue, Social Entrepreneurship, Agent of Change, Communication Model of Social Entrepreneurship

1. Introduction

Social entrepreneurship can be a precursor for community empowerment while reducing poverty (Koehne et al. 2022). This is because the practice of social entrepreneurship is able to create jobs (Kazmi et. al, 2016), eliminate gender inequality (Chatterje et. al, 2021), and increase awareness of individuals and groups to be empowered (Imron and Satrya, 2019).

In addition, social entrepreneurship can also be an instrument for overcoming social problems in society and supporting sustainable development (Bozhikin et al. 2019; Lepoutre et al. 2013; Samineni 2018). This can be seen from the impact of social entrepreneurship which can expand access to basic individual rights such as sanitation and clean water (Goyal et. al, 2021), promote inclusive education and improve health (Khalid et. al, 2022), and adaptive to climate change (Tanner et. al, 2019).

In carrying out its business, social entrepreneurship aims not only to generate profits but also to achieve social goals, and have distinct values that benefit society (Tracey and Phillips 2007; Hulgard 2010). Referring to the results of research conducted by Govender and Wu (2013), Aziz (2021), Sutowo (2020) and Rahab (2009), changes in social entrepreneurship are due to stimuli provided by something, namely the activities of reforming agents, technological characteristics and innovation. seen as able to influence people's assessment of the relative benefits they receive, as well as conformity to the values and needs of the community.

A number of studies examine the antecedents of social entrepreneurship. Urban and Teisse (2015) revealed the factors of achievement, moral judgment, empathy, and self-efficacy as determinants of social entrepreneurship. Zur (2015) makes social issues an antecedent, while Baierl et. al, (2014) makes social appraisal an antecedent. Research that uses change agents, technology and innovation, as well as communication channels as antecedents, has not been widely studied.

The agent of change is an important determinant of the success of social entrepreneurship, because of its role as a dialogue maker. Dialogue is a communication process, initiated by reforming agents who bring technological and innovation characteristics, through communication channels so that they become the driving force for community dialogue in society (Aziz 2021). Community dialogue then has an impact on community awareness to take collective action (Asia et al. 2018). Understanding the link between community dialogue and collective action can refer to a brief description from Figueroa et al. (2002), that the implementation of dialogue can make the exchange of information occur between community members so as to achieve common understanding and consensus. When these things are achieved it will underlie community members to take collective action, which in turn has an impact on changing the behavior of social entrepreneurship in society.

Previous research studies found that social entrepreneurship has full attention to community development in its environment and is able to empower it to produce a social change that leads to shared prosperity, overcomes unmet needs, and can create value (Alawiyah 2015; Dacin et al 2010; Mair and Marti 2006; Santos 2012). In the process of development communication, the process of dialogue as a form of communication related to collective action leads to solving or solving problems, producing social change in a community, and equitable sharing of information (Kincaid and Figueroa 2009). The implementation of dialogue and collective action allows community members, agents of change and related stakeholders to carry out a two-way communication process on an ongoing basis, so that an understanding and understanding is found that forms awareness of the problems and needs they feel (Asia et al. 2018).

The description of the communication model that occurs due to the role of agents of change, technology and innovation, as well as communication channels that influence community dialogue and collective action, thereby shaping behavior change related to social entrepreneurship in the MHP program, is still very minimal. So far, research on the link between the three with community dialogue and collective action regarding social entrepreneurship in the MHP program has been dominated by the fields of mechanical engineering, management, economics and community empowerment studies. Contributions to the field of communication science are still relatively minimal, especially those specifically using communication theory. The study of MHP focuses more on building electricity facilities using micro-hydro and community empowerment (Hoffken, 2016; Solihat 2020). So the purpose of this study is to analyze and formulate a communication model that describes the role of agents of change, technology and innovation as well as communication channels that influence community dialogue and collective action, thereby shaping behavior change related to social entrepreneurship in the MHP program.

2. Method

This study uses a quantitative and qualitative approach. The research population is the community in 4 villages that have a MHP program. Samples were taken as many as 200 people from a total population of 22,536 people, which were selected at simple random. Data was collected through in-depth interviews using a structured interview guide to cooperative members and members of farmer groups beneficiaries of the MHP development. Because the ultimate goal of this research is to formulate a social entrepreneurship communication model, the appropriate data processing and analysis option is SEM-PLS, and qualitative data uses data processing as proposed by Miles et al. (2014).

3. Result

One of the electricity-based social entrepreneurship programs in Indonesia is a program initiated by the People's Business and Economics Institute (IBEKA) as a non-state actor. According to Bozhikin et al. (2019), the advantages of social entrepreneurship carried out by non-state actors are program efficiency and sustainability. IBEKA organizes an electricity-based social entrepreneurship program in Bogor, Subang and Sukabumi regencies, which are also the areas of this research.

Increasing economic empowerment in society, creating the development of social entrepreneurship (Samineni 2018). Social entrepreneurship shows a process of creating new values, with an approach to conveying information to the community, so that people can increase their income (Maulinda 2018, Wibhawa 2019). The results of research conducted by Hermawati and Indra (2019), show that the communication process in groups will not be effective if the quality of leaders, the dynamics of discussions, the content of messages that are built, and the engagement of members with the group do not go well, so that in the end the effectiveness of communication has a significant positive relationship with empowerment. Meanwhile, according to Sugiyono (2009) community empowerment that is integrated with the management of water resources through micro-hydro power plants (MHP), will improve people's welfare. This is in line with Rosaira and Hermawati (2014) who see the impact of electricity on the lives of rural communities, namely the positive impact of increasing people's income and creating many new businesses, while the negative impact is the emergence of a consumptive culture.

The results of data processing with a sample of 200, with a sex ratio of 146 (73%) male and 54 (27%) female, and almost all of them follow the institutional membership formed, both cooperatives and farmer groups. In terms of work, most of them are farmers and farm laborers. The average electricity generated is between 33 – 120 KwH, this is due to the relatively abundant availability of river or spring water around the area because it is close to a large river.

Based on Figure 1 shows that there are three structural models, namely as follows:

$$Y_1 = 0,248 X_1 + 0,518 X_2 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$Y_2 = 0,292 Y_1 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$Y_3 = 0,671 Y_1 + (-0,199)Y \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Equation (1) illustrates that Community Dialogue is influenced by the support of the Characteristics of the Changing Agent (X1), the Characteristics of Technology and Innovation (X2). Of the three latent variables, namely X1 to X3, only two latent variables have a significant direct influence on community dialogue, namely the variables X1 (characteristics of reform agents) of 0.248 and X2 (characteristics of technology and innovation) of 0.518. This factor is dominant in the field because the characteristics of technology and innovation provide social benefits and can carry out social innovations. The community's need for the presence of electricity as lighting and is seen as providing convenience in opening access to information from outside, as well as the continuation of the benefits of electricity. These technologies and innovations are considered user friendly, so that the community is willing to carry out the development of the MHP in a collaborative manner.

The survey results show that the variable characteristics of reforming agents can influence respondents with their assessment of the presence of reforming agents as facilitators in providing information/knowledge and providing technical guidance on MHP development and management, as well as helping organize meetings, dialogues, expressing opinions and cooperation, as well as the intensity in helping the community to get help from stakeholders, so that they can fulfill the legal requirements for electrification development (MHP) very well. Almost the entire community accepts the MHP development, because it can provide great benefits in terms of finding information related to increasing business activities and other information they need.

Figure 1: Standardized Fit Model Values

The support of technological characteristics and innovations that are brought, namely MHP, has a significant influence on the added value of electrification utilization, because the people feel they really need information which they have not got so far. Technology and innovation that provide a level of relative advantage and the level of suitability of technology and innovation are assessed by the community on the benefits and benefits received from the MHP development, as well as the level of suitability with values, past experiences and the needs of the community for the MHP development.

In community dialogue, out of 10 indicators, only 3 indicators had a direct influence on community dialogue, namely Y1.1 (acknowledgment of a problem), Y1.7 (setting of goals), and Y1.8 (choice of action). The survey results show that on the acknowledgment indicator that there is a problem, all members of the community state that the lack of lighting (electricity) is a common problem. Then the community held a large meeting to discuss various aspects of managing and building the MHP, which they felt would help them gain insight. In addition, the community also sets goals to be achieved with the MHP development. Another indicator that directly influences community dialogue is determining the actions to be achieved in accordance with the goals set. The goal is for the village community to get electric lighting from the MHP construction, that way they can get and seek information from outside their area, this is felt to be able to help the community from various aspects of their life. At the time of making decisions in the household to get electricity assistance and become members of cooperatives/farmer groups as many as 99 people (49.25 percent) were made by means of discussion or discussion between family members to reach an agreement, while as many as 98 people (48.76 percent) it was

decided by the head of the household, and only 4 people (1.99 percent) stated that it was decided by the management.

Equation (2) shows that community dialogue influences collective action at Y2.1 (assignment of responsibilities), Y2.2 (mobilization of community resources), Y2.4 (utilization of the results achieved), and Y2.5 (participatory evaluation). The survey results show that in community dialogues held in large meetings, the community is invited to choose a person in charge who will manage and maintain the micro hydro turbine. In addition, the community was also invited to form formal and legal institutions, whether in the form of cooperative institutions or farmer groups, and all communities expressed their consent to form a formal institution to manage the maintenance of the MHP. Mobilizing community resources by mutual cooperation in assisting MHP development activities, it is hoped that there will be a sense of togetherness and ownership to jointly maintain from construction to management of the MHP.

From the results of in-depth interviews with the community regarding electricity needs in their area:

"the people really need electricity, so far they have used cempor"

"glad there is electricity, so bright at night"

"can hold religious activities or gather at night"

"kids can study at night"

Then about how to build PLMH:

"everything if done together will definitely feel light"

"We all take part in transporting the paralons, pulling the cables for the construction of the turbines"

"All people participate in the construction of this turbine, by working together, sharing work, ladies and gentlemen, even teenagers also help"

Utilization of the results felt by the community as a whole, evaluation activities from the construction of the MHP, were also carried out jointly by the community.

"It's better if it's still there, because if you rely on PLN, the electricity tends to turn on and off"

"the activities carried out by the cooperative are being improved again"

Equation (3) on the variables Y1 (community dialogue) and Y2 (collective action), Y1 has a direct effect on the level of social entrepreneurship of 0.671, while Y2 has a negative effect (-0.199). This is because, almost 90 percent of the community, when a large meeting is held, they are present but they do not actively express their opinions, suggestions or suggestions. Most of them accept decisions when there is already someone who is considered to understand more than them, and that's only a very small number. Variables Y1 and Y2 influence the use of social entrepreneurship in carrying out social innovation (Y3.2) and economic activities (Y3.3). The survey results show that the presence of MHP has an impact on technology acceptance which ultimately causes the community to carry out various social innovations, such as providing scholarships for school children, so that many children can continue their studies to a higher level, in addition to making health service facilities easier. and there are no fees. Meanwhile, economic activities are described in capital loans provided by cooperatives/farmer groups, which can provide opportunities for the community to own other businesses or increase the scale of existing businesses.

4. Discussion

Figuroa et al. (2002), Asia et al. (2018), states that the implementation of dialogue can make the exchange of information occur between community members so as to achieve common understanding and consensus. In addition to community dialogue, it also has an impact on public awareness to take collective action. The dialogue carried out by the community receiving MHP assistance included determining who would receive electricity assistance, how to build a turbine house to produce electricity, and the selection of turbine guards. While collective action includes carrying out mutual cooperation activities during the construction of the turbine house until it finally produces electricity.

Hulgard (2010), explains that there are four main elements in social entrepreneurship, among others, social values, civil society, innovation, and economic activity. Meanwhile and Cukier et al. (2011), stated that social entrepreneurship involves the creation of innovations and business activities. Cooperative members and members of farmer groups after taking action collectively, they develop social entrepreneurship by making social innovations, namely holding scholarships for school children, and creating health service facilities. Meanwhile, economic activities are carried out by providing capital loans for new businesses or increasing the scale of existing businesses.

5. Conclusion

Community Dialogue is influenced by the support of Characteristics of Changing Agents (X1) and Characteristics of Technology and Innovation (X2). The most dominant factor influencing Community Dialogue is Technology and Innovation Characteristics of 0.518.

Collective Action is influenced by community dialogue support (Y1), with a significance value of 0.292. The communication activity carried out is conveying the results of discussion of various activities, both new plans and those that will be carried out by the cooperative/farmer group to its members. This discussion activity was not attended by all of its members, but only the management of the cooperative/farmer group.

Social entrepreneurship (Y3) is influenced by communication dialogue of 0.671, and collective action (Y2) with a value of -0.199. The presence of MHP has an impact on social entrepreneurship on indicators of carrying out social innovation activities in the community and economic activities in the MHP program.

The social entrepreneurship communication model for the MHP program is built by the characteristics of reform agents and the characteristics of technology and innovation that influence community dialogue and collective action. Meanwhile, communication channels do not affect community dialogue. Community dialogue and collective action act as a driving force for residents to change social entrepreneurial behavior. Community dialogue and collective action influence social entrepreneurship communication on indicators of social innovation and economic activity in the MHP program. This model can be applied by looking at the same type of geography and topography of an area.

References

- Alawiyah, DN. (2015). *Socioteenpreneur*. Publisher Erlangga : Surabaya
- Asia, N., Sarwoprosodjo, S., Gandasari, D. (2018). Dialogue and Collective Action of Farmer Groups in the Cocoa Certification Program in West Sulawesi Province. *Journal of Development Communication*, eISSN 2442-4102, February 2018, Volume 16, No. 1.
- Aziz, A. (2021). *Development of a Communication Model between Parties in the Implementation of an Integrated Information Technology-Based Planting Calendar Information System*. [Unpublished Desertation]. IPB University.
- Bozhikin, I., Macke, J., and da Costa, L. F. (2019). The role of government and key non-state actors in social entrepreneurship: A systematic literature review. *Journal of cleaner production*, 226, 730-747. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.076>.
- Chatterjee, I., Cornelissen, J., and Wincent, J. (2021). Social Entrepreneurship and Values Work: The role of practices in shaping values and negotiating change. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 36(1), 106064.
- Dacin, P.A., Dacin, M.T., and Matear, M. (2010). 'Social entrepreneurship: why we don't need a new theory and how we move forward from here', *Academy of Management Perspectives*, Vol 24, No 3, pp 37-57. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00909880701434265>.
- Figuroa ME, Kincaid DL, Rani M, and Lewis G. (2002). *Communication For Social Change: An Integrated Model For Measuring The Process and Its Outcomes*. *The Communication for Social Change Working Paper Series: No.1*. New York (USA). <http://www.communicationforsocialchange.org/pdf/socialchange.pdf>.
- Goyal, S., Agrawal, A., and Sergi, B. S. (2021). Social Entrepreneurship for Scalable Solutions Addressing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at BoP in India. *Qualitative Research in Organizations and Management*, 16(3-4), 509-529. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QROM-07-2020-1992>

- Govender JP, and Wu J. (2013). The adoption of internet banking in a developing economy. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*. 5(8):496-504.
- Hermawati, W dan Indra. (2019). Local Leadership and Microhydro Project Sustainability in Rural Indonesia. *Journals.sagepub.com/home/ipa*. DOI: 10.1177/0019556119844558.
- Hoffken J I. (2016). Demystification and localization in the adoption of micro-hydro technology: Insights from India. *Energy Research and Social Science journal home page: www.elsevier.com/locate/erss*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2016.09.002>.
- Imron, D. K., and Satrya, A. R. A. (2019). Women and coffee farming: Collective consciousness towards social entrepreneurship in Ulubelu, Lampung. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Ilmu Politik*, 22(3), 216-229. doi: 10.22146/jsp.35366.
- Isti'adah FNL. (2017). Student Interpersonal Communication Profile. *Journal of Innovative Counseling : Theory, Practice and Research*. 1(1):40-49.
- Kazmi, S. A., Hashim, M., Kee, D. H., and Khan, F. U. (2016). Social entrepreneurship and its impact on economy: In perspective of Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(4), 161-166.
- Khalid, S., Dixon, S., and Vijayasingham, L. (2022). The gender responsiveness of social entrepreneurship in health—A review of initiatives by Ashoka fellows. *Social Science and Medicine*, 293, 114665. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114665>.
- Kincaid DL, and Figueroa ME. (2009). *Communication for Participatory Development: Dialogue, Action, and Change*. In Frey LR, Cissna KN, editor. *Routledge Handbook Of Applied Communication Research*. New York (USA): Routledge. page 506-531. <http://www.pdfdrive.com/routledge-handbook-of-applied-communication-research-e25485975.html>.
- Koehne, F., Woodward, R., and Honig, B. (2022). The potentials and perils of prosocial power: Transnational social entrepreneurship dynamics in vulnerable places. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 37(4), 106206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2022.106206>.
- Mair, J., and Marti, I. (2006). 'Social entrepreneurship research: a source of explanation, prediction, and delight', *Journal of World Business*, Vol 41, No 1, pp 36–44. doi:10.1016/j.jwb.2005.09.002.
- Maulinda. (2018). Proses Pengembangan Social Enterprise Agriculture: Studi Biografi pada Agradaya. *Jurnal Studi Pemuda*, vol 7 no 2 tahun 2018. <http://doi.org/10.22146/studipemudaugm.40114>.
- Piotrow, P.T., Kincaid, D. L., Rimon, J.G. II, and Rinehart, W. (1997). *Health Communication: Lessons from Family Planning and Reproductive Health*, Westport, Conn.: Praeger.
- Rahab. (2009). The Relationship between Technology Characteristics and Likelihood of Small Businesses Adopting TI. *Jurnal Bisnis dan Ekonomi (JBE)*. 16(2):111-125.
- Riadi E. (2018). *Statistical SEM-Structural Equation Modeling with LISREL*. Yogyakarta.
- Sahrakorpi, T., and Bandi, V. (2021). Empowerment or employment? Uncovering the paradoxes of social entrepreneurship for women via Husk Power Systems in rural North India. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 79, 102153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102153>.
- Rosaira, I., dan Hermawati W. (2014). *The Impact of MHP on The Socio_Economic Life of the Community in Gunung Sawur Hamlet, Sumber Rejo Village, Candipuro, Lumajang*. [Paper Presentation] Proceeding of the 2014 National Appropriate Technology Conference and Seminar.
- Samineni S. (2018). Social Entrepreneurship – As a Tool for Sustainable Development of Women in Rural India Leading to Economic Empowerment. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*. DOI: 10.9790/487X-2002079198.
- Santos, F.M. (2012). 'A positive theory of social entrepreneurship', *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol 111, No 3, pp 335–351. DOI 10.1007/s10551-012-1413-4.
- Solihat I. (2020). Design Prototype of Micro-hydro Power Plant. *Jurnal Inovasi Ilmu Pengetahuan dan Teknologi*, Vol 1 no 2.
- Sugiyono, A. (2009). Community Empowerment in Managing the Potential of Water Resources through the Development of PLTMH. *JESP Vol. 1, No.3*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/275648936>.
- Sutowo I R. (2020). Partisipatory Communication in the Development of Social Entrepreneurship in Pandeglang, Banten. *EXOPSE : Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi Vol. 3, No. 01, April, 2020*. DOI: 10.33021/exp.v3i1.885.
- Tracey, P., and Phillips, N. (2007). The distinctive challenge of educating social entrepreneurs: A postscript and rejoinder to the special issue on entrepreneurship education. *Academy of management learning and education*, 6(2), 264-271. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228315021_The_Distinctive_Challenge_of_Educating_Social_Entrepreneurs_A_Post-Script_and_Rejoinder_to_the_Special_Issue_on_Entrepreneurship_Education.
- Urban, B., and Teise, H. (2015). Antecedents to social entrepreneurship intentions: An empirical study in South Africa. *Management Dynamics: Journal of the Southern African Institute for Management Scientists*, 24(2), 36-52.

- Wibhawa B. (2018). IBEKA's social service delivery model in Indonesia's micro-hydro power. *Human Systems Management* 37 (2018) 387–397 IOS Press. DOI 10.3233/HSM-171628.
- Žur, A. (2015). Social problems as sources of opportunity—antecedents of social entrepreneurship opportunities. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 3(4), 73-87.